

WEAVE's 3D modelling tools, ICH and the SCHEDAR project

Computing advances and 3D digitization of human motion and systems provide challenges for the novice and software can be expensive and inaccessible to some end users. With this in mind, the [SCHEDAR](#) team and developers are committed to devising a set of guidelines and frameworks for tools that influence existing Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) motion databases. Within WEAVE, dance is central to our work and ICH is an important component of the 3D modelling research questions. This LabDay brought together the WEAVE and SCHEDAR team members and the event discussed how each project envisages making ICH content digitally available to facilitate the preservation and safeguarding of cultural heritage while also ensuring that the development of technology develops in accordance with and aligns with the needs of key stakeholders.

Themes explored at the event included:

- How might we explore alternative modes of collaboration and ensuring that the cultural/dance communities we are including are guiding research questions and aggregation processes while also unpacking and rethinking the ethical politics that emerge when digitising intangible content and deconstructing narratives?
- How might a new digital cycle for ICH impact on the safeguarding and disseminating forms of ICH such as dance, especially in terms of challenging dance's oft-cited ontology as ephemeral and immaterial?
- How to create a continuum whereby digital tools that enable new forms of 'capture' and 'dissemination' of content (and the important focus in WEAVE on 'bottom-up' approaches by directly involving the communities who create and practice the content, to ensuring that content is 'authentic' and follows proper ethical codes) through to, on the other hand, tools that emphasise engagement through being able to 'move with' the content?
- How to make the digital tools, and hence the content, accessible, in ways that are cognisant of the communities who want to engage?

Key takeaways:

- There is cope to work much further on the digital interweaving of tangible and intangible heritage – how to solve the problem of people-less environments and the 'uncanny valley'? How might CH representation address this?
- The value of co-design sessions - the specificity of detail for 3D annotation, working with community experts
- The value of digital annotation for ICH practices beyond dance and movement e.g. weaving - layering CH activity with movement
- The value of AR as a teaching tool for movement and ICH practices

Video: <https://youtu.be/YRHyDzcsdes>